

Seamless-PV

D3.2 Flexible tabber-stringer compatible with new cell formats, Zebra technology and ECA-based tabber stringer compatible with black ribbon technology, complying with specifications

Task 3.2. Flexible tabber-stringer for mono and polycrystalline cell interconnection of upcoming cell formats.

Task 3.3. Flexible tabber-stringers for Zebra-cell technology interconnection with enhanced flexibility

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SEAMLESS-PV PROJECT

A novel manufacturing process for integrated photovoltaics

Integrated photovoltaics (IPVs) have demonstrated their success and impact in their use as building-integrated photovoltaics. They are also considered promising in several other sectors. Their adaptation to other industries or devices could offer surprising benefits. Unfortunately, the very need for adaptable IPV solutions hinders their expansion as their current manufacturing processes cannot create IPV solutions customised to each sector. The EU-funded SEAMLESS-PV project aims to tackle this by developing revolutionary tools for photovoltaic manufacturing as well as new IPV products that offer improved efficiency, adaptability and integrability while at the same time showcasing their cost-effectiveness in comparison to competitors.

The title of SEAMLESS-PV project is *“Development of advanced manufacturing equipment and processes aimed at the seamless integration of multifunctional PV solutions, enabling the deployment of IPV sectors”*. SEAMLESS-PV is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action started in January 2023 that will continue through December 2026.

More information can be found at:

<https://www.seamlesspv.eu/>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096126>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D3.2 explains the process carried out for the manufacturing of two different machines:

- 1- Flexible tabber-stringer for mono and polycrystalline cell interconnection of upcoming cell formats.
- 2- Flexible tabber-stringers for Zebra-cell technology interconnection with enhanced flexibility.

In this deliverable, the machines are shown from a functional point of view, visually showing the different positions that make up the machines, so that the machines and how they work can be understood.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of the deliverable content and purpose

MASS has experience in previous projects in manufacturing tabber-stringers with extra capacities respect to the ones defined as standard, for example the tabber-stringer developed in the BIPVBoost project. Within the SEAMLESS-PV project, the development goes one step further in giving extra specifications to the tabber-stringer, thus manufacturing two tabber-stringers with extra capacities to what the current market offers.

In this DEMO type deliverable, the two machines developed within tasks T3.2 and T3.3 of the SEAMLESS-PV project are shown graphically. These machines are:

- 1- Flexible tabber-stringer for mono and polycrystalline cell interconnection of upcoming cell formats.
- 2- Flexible tabber-stringers for Zebra-cell technology interconnection with enhanced flexibility

Both processes and functionalities of the machines will be described in greater detail in D3.5.

1.2 Relation with other activities in the project

Table 1.1 depicts the main links of this deliverable to other activities (work packages, tasks, deliverables, etc.) within SEAMLESS project. The table should be considered along with the current document for further understanding of the deliverable contents and purpose.

Table 1.1: Relation between current deliverable and other activities in the project

Project activity	Relation with current deliverable
T3.1	For the manufacturing of the tabber-stringer, the specifications defined in D3.1 have been taken into account.

1.3 List of abbreviations

Table 1.2: List of abbreviations

Acronyms	Meaning
BIPV	Building Integrated Photovoltaics
ECA	Electrically Conductive Adhesive

2 Flexible tabber-stringer for mono and polycrystalline cell interconnection of upcoming cell formats.

This tabber-stringer can work in two different modes with mono and polycrystalline cells:

1. Standard mode: Mode with constant distance between cells.
2. BIPV mode: Mode with variable distance between cells between 2 and 200 mm

2.1 Complete machine

Figure 2.1: Complete tabber-stringer.

2.2 Ribbon feed control

Figure 2.2: Ribbon feed configuration.

2.3 Cell feeder (M10 full or half)

Figure 2.3: Cells feeder.

2.4 Cell position control by camera

Figure 2.4: Cell position control by camera.

2.5 Ribbon dispenser-placer with innovative system that allows different lengths between cells

Figure 2.5: Ribbon dispenser & placer for string.

2.6 Welding (using a process developed for this machine)

Figure 2.6: Welding area.

2.7 String cutting

Figure 2.7: String cutting station.

2.8 String finished

Figure 2.8: String samples, 1x Standard mode+ 2 X BIPV mode.

D3.2_Flexible tabber-stringer compatible with new cell formats, Zebra technology and ECA-based tabber stringer compatible with black ribbon technology, complying with specifications

3 Flexible tabber-stringer for Zebra-cell technology interconnection with enhanced flexibility

In this tabber-stringer, strings will be manufactured using Zebra Cells by using ECA for the ribbon-cell bond.

3.1 Complete machine

Figure 3.1: Complete tabber-stringer.

3.2 Ribbon feed control

Figure 3.2: Ribbon feed configuration.

3.3 Cell feeder (Zebra M6 half)

Figure 3.3: Cells feeder.

3.4 Cell position control by camera

Figure 3.4: Cell position control by camera.

3.5 ECA dispensing system

Figure 3.5: New ECA dispensing system.

3.6 Ribbon dispenser-placer with innovative system that allows different lengths between cells

Figure 3.6: Ribbon dispenser-placer for string designed for SEAMLESS-PV T3.3.

D3.2_Flexible tabber-stringer compatible with new cell formats, Zebra technology and ECA-based tabber stringer compatible with black ribbon technology, complying with specifications

3.7 Welding (using a process developed for this machine)

Figure 3.7: Welding (process developed for Zebra+ECA)

3.8 String cutting

Figure 3.8: String cutting station.

4 Summary

This deliverable graphically shows the work carried out to manufacture the machines defined in tasks T3.2 and T3.3 of the SEAMLESS-PV project.

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